

The Beautiful System

Numbers and Symbols are interchangeably units, values, or lengths in metres, as appropriate. $\approx$ is “engineering equals” as opposed to mathematical equals =. So 3.14159265... $\approx$ 3.1416.

- $\pi \approx 3.1416$
- $\varphi \approx 1.618$
- $\varphi^2 \approx 2.618$
- $e \approx 2.7183$
- $\acute{e} = e - 1 = e - m = 1.7183$
- $m = \text{metre} = 1.000$
- $\mathbb{C} = \text{royal cubit} = \pi/6 = 0.5236$
- $f = \text{foot} \approx \mathbb{C}/\acute{e} \approx 0.5236/1.7183 \approx 0.30472$
- $Y \approx \text{“megalithic yard”} \approx \mathbb{C} + f \approx 0.5236 + 0.30472 \approx 0.82832$
- $M = \text{Grand Metre} = m + \mathbb{C} = 1.5236 \approx 5 \text{ feet}$
- $S = \text{six feet (fathom)} = m + \mathbb{C} + f \approx 1.82832$

$$\frac{\pi}{6} = \frac{\varphi^2}{5} = \pi - \varphi^2 = \mathbb{C}$$

$$\frac{\pi+1}{e} = \frac{\varphi^2}{\acute{e}} \left(= \frac{\varphi+1}{e-1} \right) = \pi - \varphi = \mathbb{C} + 1 = M$$

$$\frac{\mathbb{C}}{f} \approx \frac{e\mathbb{C}}{Y} \approx \frac{\acute{e}}{m} \approx \frac{\varphi^2}{M} \approx \frac{\pi}{S} \approx \acute{e} \approx 1.7183$$

This links the three key irrationals: π , φ , and e ,

with three base units of length: **foot**, (royal) **cubit**, and **metre**,

and three derived lengths: “**megalithic yard**”, **five feet** (grand metre), and **six feet**,

via a consistent ratio of $\acute{e}$.